

Assessing the 5a Factors Affecting the Utilization of Primary Health Care Services Among Reproductive Age Women in Ogun State

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Abstract

The study assessed the 5A factors affecting the utilization of primary health care services among reproductive age women in Ogun State. The study specifically examined association between 5A's of access (accessibility, affordability, availability, accommodation, and acceptability) and utilization of primary health care services among reproductive age women. The study adopted a descriptive cross sectional research design. The population of the study consisted of reproductive age women attending Primary health care centres in Odeda Local Government Area, Ogun State. The sample size of 386 women was selected for this study it was calculated using Slovin's formula. Multistage sampling procedure was used to choose the sample for this study. Data from the respondents was collected with the use of researcher-designed questionnaire. Face and content of the questionnaire were ensured. Data collected through a pilot study was computed using Cronbach Alpha test which yielded reliability coefficient value of 0.811. Two research assistants were employed to assist in the distribution and collection of questionnaires. The researchers and their assistants ensured that the questionnaires were properly filled before retrieval from the respondents. The data obtained was analysed using inferential statistics of Chi-square at 0.05 level of significance. The study revealed that accessibility ($x^2 = 23.965$, $p = .000$); affordability ($x^2 = 19.655$, $p = .000$); availability is ($x^2 = 31.770$, $p = .012$);

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accommodation is ($\chi^2 = 14.099$, $p = .000$); and acceptability is ($\chi^2 = 9.832$, $p = .023$) were factors associated with utilization of primary health care services by reproductive age women. It was recommended among others that cost of services should be reconsidered and more funding should be provided for health in the budget.

Keywords: 5A Factors, Utilization, Primary Health Care Service, Reproductive age women,

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Introduction

Primary health care is rooted in a commitment to social justice and equity and in the recognition of the fundamental right to the highest attainable standard of health, as echoed in Article 25 of the Universal Declaration on Human Rights: “Everyone has the right to a standard of living adequate for the health and wellbeing of himself and of his family, including food, clothing, housing and medical care and necessary social services. According to WHO, (2015), the concept of primary health care has been repeatedly reinterpreted and redefined. In some contexts, it has referred to the provision of ambulatory or first-level of personal health care services. In other contexts, primary health care has been understood as a set of priority health interventions for low-income populations (also called selective primary health care). Others have understood primary health care as an essential component of human development, focusing on the economic, social and political aspects.

WHO has developed a cohesive definition based on three components; 1) meeting people’s health needs through comprehensive promotive, protective, preventive, curative, rehabilitative, and palliative care throughout the life course, strategically prioritizing key health care services aimed at individuals and families through primary care and the population through public health functions as the central elements of integrated health services; 2) systematically addressing the broader determinants of health (including social, economic, environmental, as well as people’s characteristics and behaviours) through evidence-informed public policies and actions across all sectors; and 3) empowering individuals, families, and communities to optimize their health, as advocates for policies that promote and protect health and well-being, as co-developers of health and social services, and as self-carers and care-givers to others. Okonofua, et al (2019), reported that the Federal Government of Nigeria has adopted Primary Health Care (PHC) as a policy to achieve universal health coverage for citizens and to ensure that women of childbearing age, especially in rural areas, gain access to evidence-based skilled pregnancy care, immunization, family planning and other health services for the prevention of maternal morbidity and mortality.

Access to health care is defined as having timely use of personal health services to achieve the best possible health outcome. Access requires gaining entry into the health-care system, getting access to sites of care where patients can receive needed services, and finding providers who meet the needs of patients and with whom patients can develop a relationship based on mutual communication and trust. Clinicians note that timely access to health care is important inasmuch as it might enable patients and physicians to prevent illness, control acute episodes, or manage chronic conditions, any of which could avoid exacerbation or complication of health conditions (NCHS, 2017).

There are many ways to think of access, and the term access is often used to describe factors or characteristics that influence one's initial contact with or use of services. Anderson and Newman (2005) present a framework of health-care utilization that includes predisposing factors, enabling factors, and need factors. They saw access as the opportunity to identify health-care needs; to reach, obtain, or use primary healthcare services; and to have the need for services fulfilled. Access can be seen as a continuum: even if care is available, many factors can affect ease of access to it, for example, the availability of providers who will

accept a person's insurance (including Medicaid), ease in making an appointment with a given provider, the ability of a patient to pay for care (even if a patient is insured, due to cost-sharing co-payments and deductibles), and the difficulty of arranging transportation to and from healthcare facilities (MACPAC, 2016).

One of the underlying causes of high maternal mortality in the community is barriers to accessing primary health care services (Kyei-Nimakoh, et al, 2017). Soma-Pillay and Pattinson, (2016) found that many influencing factors could affect the overall accessibility and utilization of primary healthcare facilities (MHFs). Calvello, et al (2015) reported that identifying the accessibility issues to maternal health in Nigeria could guide decision-makers' to take the required measures towards appropriate and equitable primary healthcare, which can help transform the socio-economic status of people living in the community. In light of the current efforts of the UN for the new SDGs to 2030 to provide equitable health access and reduce maternal mortality.

In recent quantitative study carried out by Lorretta, et al (2019) claim that the same communities where this qualitative study was conducted showed that less than 47% of pregnant women gave birth in PHC centres, while 25% gave birth at home even when PHC facilities are presumably located in districts close to where the women live. The results of their study identified diverse reasons with detailed explanations as to why women do not use PHC facilities for pregnancy care in the two LGAs. The reasons proffered can be broadly categorized into 1) accessibility factors – poor roads, difficulty with transportation, long distances to PHC facilities and that the PHC centres are not always open; and 2) high costs of services, which include the inability to pay for services even when costs are not excessive, and the introduction of informal payments by staff.. The study further revealed that the cost of services was an important consideration for women and their partner in reaching decisions to seek pregnancy care in PHC centres, it was clear that if services are of better quality (with better availability of skilled providers and facilities), and with the facilities being more easily accessible, women will be ready to pay total costs of services. Contrary to our expectations, women's lack of knowledge about the need for skilled pregnancy care and cultural or normative preferences did not feature as reasons for non-use of PHC for skilled pregnancy care.

Mugo, et al (2018) also showed in their review the importance of infrastructure for primary health care services. Pregnant women report poor infrastructure of health facilities, prolonged waiting times, and lack of clean water supply, experienced healthcare professionals, and sufficient bed capacity. Even when women need to utilize primary health care services, they are reluctant to go due to the bad reputation of primary health care services and the perceived poor quality of care. According to World Bank insecurity can stop people from accessing primary health care facilities due to fear of attacks. Due to conflicts worldwide, 95% of the displaced refugees live in developing countries, which exerts further financial and healthcare burden on reproductive age women. The study specifically examines factors that influence the choice of health-care system by the reproductive age women and the results show that factors such as distance from health care facility, belief system, quality of health service received and finance were important determinants of choice of Health Care System utilized by reproductive age women. They suggested that low-income, uneducated

women should be targeted for enlightenment in addition to promoting education of the girl-child and women empowerment.

Ovikuomagbe (2017) found that several studies have shown that income, education, distance, amongst others played significant roles in enabling women seek healthcare services. Titus, (2015) showed that most rural households in Nigeria had the challenge of inaccessibility of modern healthcare facilities. This includes long distance to such healthcare facilities. Osubor et al (2016) claims that Poor health seeking behaviours in terms of low antenatal care use, postnatal care use, and skilled birth attendant at delivery exist in rural Nigeria. Say and Raine (2017) found that the differences in the use of primary health care services in developing countries was attributed to age, education, medical insurance and distance to health facility.

Ahmad, et al (2019) research study found that 82.6% of the respondents opined that availability of health care personnel influence their utilization of the primary health care facility, while 17.3% of the respondents said no. While, 40.2% of the respondents opined that availability of drugs influence their utilization of primary health care facility, 59.8% of the respondents opined that non-availability of drugs influence them non-utilization of primary health care facility. Similarly, 73.7% claimed that timely service delivery influence their utilization of primary health care facility, while 26.3% disagree with such claim and 69.4% of the respondents claimed accessibility of service with ease influence their utilization of primary health care facility, while 30.6% disagree. This implies that certain factors influence the utilization and non-utilization of health care facility in the study area. In other words, there are myriads of factors that affect the utilization of PHC.

The main objective of the study was to assess the 5A factors affecting the utilization of primary health care services among reproductive age women in Ogun State. The study specifically examined association between 5A's of access (accessibility, affordability, availability, accommodation, and acceptability) and utilization of primary health care services among reproductive age women.

Ho1: There is no significant association between 5A's of access (accessibility, affordability, availability, accommodation, and acceptability) and utilization of primary health care services among reproductive age women.

Conceptual Framework

Figure i: Conceptual Framework on the model of 5A’s Factors influencing Utilization of Primary Health Care Services

Application of the Model

The conceptual model was developed to understand the basis of the study. The framework was developed with the help of extensive literature review and was modified from the Anderson and Newman framework of health care services utilization, which provides a framework for assessing factors influencing utilization of primary health care services among reproductive age women in Odeda Local Government, Ogun State. Application of this framework to the study identified the behavioural characteristics of the reproductive

age women in Odeda Local Government Area of Ogun State that provides measures of their access to primary health care services.

The behavioural model proposed by Anderson and Newman identified characteristics that determines the utilization of primary health care services (Such as general out – patient care, in – Patient care, Antenatal care, post-natal care, Delivery, immunization, family planning etc.) by reproductive age women . The model further identify factors and needs as a measures of accessing the utilization of primary health care services in which the factors are characteristics that are actually grouped into the 5A's of access. These are accessibility, affordability, availability, accommodation and acceptability. And while the needs are the most immediate determinants of primary health care services utilization and it suggests that the use of primary health care services can be influenced by a women's knowledge and perception of the relative importance of primary health care services.

- **Accessibility** refers to the geographical and dimensions of access, which tends to explain how easily the reproductive age women can physically reach the primary health care providers location in terms of long distance to PHC facility and poor road.
- **Affordability** is an index of how the primary health care services providers charge the reproductive age woman and how the cost of care relate to the willingness to pay for services such as cost of drugs and services, income and poverty.
- **Accommodation** this refers to extent to which the providers operation is organized in ways that meets the constraints and preferences of the reproductive age women, of great concern are hours of operation and the ability of the reproductive age women to access irrespective of status or prior appointment such as waiting time, competent staff, attitude of health care providers, opening of facilities for 24hours.
- **Availability** this denotes the extent to which primary health care providers possess the requisite resources, such as personnel and technology to meet the needs of the reproductive age women.
- **Acceptability** this is the extent to which the reproductive age women is comfortable with the nature of service with to their culture, religion and other social dimensions such as quality of care received and community participation.

Methodology

The study adopted a descriptive cross sectional research design. The population of the study consisted of reproductive age women attending Primary health care centres in Odeda Local Government Area, Ogun State. The sample size of 386 women was selected for this study it was calculated using Slovin's formula. Multistage sampling procedure was used to choose the sample for this study. Odeda Local Government Area is divided into 10 political ward, only 6 wards has PHCs with a total of 16 PHCs in all.

Stage 1: Odeda Local Government Area was divided into 10 wards (See Table 1 below)

Table 1: Lists of 10 Wards in Odeda Local Government

Wards	Name
Ward 1	Alabata
Ward 2	Alagbagba
Ward 3	Itesi
Ward 4	Ilugun
Ward 5	Obantoko
Ward 6	Obese
Ward 7	Odeda

Ward 8	Olodo
Ward 9	Opeji
Ward 10	Osiele

Stage 2: Out of the 10 wards in Odeda Local Government Area, six (6) was selected because they have PHCs (See Table 2)

Table 2 Primary Health Care Distribution in 6 Wards in Odeda LGA

S/n		Name	Number of PHCs
1	Ward 3	Itesi	3 PHCs
2	Ward 4	Ilugun	4 PHCs
3	Ward 5	Obantoko	4 PHCs
4	Ward 7	Odeda	2 PHCs
5	Ward 9	Opeji	2 PHCs
6	Ward 10	Osiele	1 PHC
		Total	16 PHCs

Stage 3: From each of the wards with PHCs, 2 PHCs were selected. Mainly because they have client weekly attendance of 40 and above, some PHCs were selected purposively because they were the only PHCs in the ward and also had client weekly flow of above 40. This gave a total of 11 participating PHCs in all (see Table 3). These PHCs have the highest number of women attendance.

Table 3: Number of PHCs that have highest number of reproductive age women in Attendance in Odeda LGA and their attendance per week

S/n	Ward	Name of Facility	Weekly Flow
1	Ward 3: ITESI	Emulu health clinic	48
		Ntoji health clinic	42
2	Ward 4: ILUGUN	Ilugun health clinic	50
		Olokemeji health clinic	50
3	Ward 5: OBANKOTO	Obatonko HC	60
		Eleweran HC	55
		Lakiri HC	45
4	Ward 7: ODEDA	Baagbon health clinic	75
		Baba Pupa health clinic	50
5	Ward 9: OPEJI	Bode Olude PHC	41
6	Ward 10: OSIELE	Osiele HC	45

Stage 4: Proportionate simple random sampling technique was used to select 386 reproductive age women from these PHCs.

A proportionate number of respondents for each of the eleven (11) PHCs were calculated by adopting this formula:

$$\frac{Q \times n_0}{N}$$

Where Q = the number of reproductive age women in each PHC

n_0 = sample size of finite population

N = finite population size (Total number of reproductive age women selected from the 11 PHCs)

The sample size of 386 was distributed in proportions as follows;

Number of women

$$\frac{\text{Total Number of women in all PHCs}}{\text{X Sample size.}} = \text{xx}$$

Total Number of women in all PHCs

Table 4: Calculated proportion of reproductive women for selected PHCs

S/n	Name of facility	Population	Proportion	Sample size
1	Emulu health clinic	192	$192/2244 \times 386 = 33$	33
2	Ntoji health clinic	168	$168/2244 \times 386 = 29$	29
3	Ilugun health clinic	200	$200/2244 \times 386 = 34$	34
4	Olokemeji health clinic	200	$200/2244 \times 386 = 34$	34
5	Obatonko HC	240	$240/2244 \times 386 = 41$	41
6	Lakiri HC	180	$180/2244 \times 386 = 31$	31
7	Baagbon health clinic	300	$300/2244 \times 386 = 52$	52
8	Baba Pupa health clinic	200	$200/2244 \times 386 = 34$	34
9	Opeji HC	180	$180/2244 \times 386 = 31$	31
10	Bode Olude PHC	164	$164/2244 \times 386 = 28$	28
11	Osiele HC	220	$220/2244 \times 386 = 38$	38
	TOTAL	2244		386

Selection of the reproductive age women was done using simple random sampling technique in which samples of 386 reproductive women were selected.

Data from the respondents was collected with the use of researcher-designed questionnaire. The question was divided into two (2) sections which are A and B. Section A gathered information on demographic and socioeconomic characteristics data of respondents and while section B gathered information on 5A's of access factors influencing utilization of primary health care services which consists of 19 items that sought to know if the 5A's factors such as accessibility, affordability, availability, accommodation and acceptability influence utilization of PHC services. Face and content of the questionnaire were ensured. The reliability of the instrument was established by a pilot test using internal consistency method. Data collected was computed using Cronbach Alpha test which yielded reliability coefficient value of 0.811. The coefficient value was high enough to guarantee the reliability of the instrument.

Two research assistants were employed to assist in the distribution and collection of questionnaires. The researchers and her assistants ensured that the questionnaires were properly filled before retrieval from the respondents. The data obtained was analysed using inferential statistics of Chi-square at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Ho1: There is no significant association between 5A's of access (accessibility, affordability, availability, accommodation, and acceptability) and utilization of primary health care services among reproductive age women.

Table 5: Association between 5A's of access and utilization of primary health care services among reproductive age women

Other Factors	Yes	No	Don't know	X ²	P
Accessibility					
Long distance to PHC facility	265(72.2)	88(24.0)	14(3.8)	23.965	.000
Poor transportation services	190(51.8)	100(27.2)	77(21.0)		
Poor road	233(63.5)	111(30.2)	23(6.3)		
Facility not opened for 24 hours	-	367(100.0)	-		
Affordability					
High cost of drug and services	172(46.9)	130(35.4)	65(17.7)	19.655	.000
Income and Poverty	91(24.8)	100(27.2)	176(48.0)		
Introduction of informal payment by staff	67(18.3)	188(51.2)	112(30.5)		
Availability					
Inadequate number of Staff	201(54.8)	123(33.5)	43(11.7)	31.770	.012
Lack of essential drugs	187(50.9)	150(40.9)	30(8.2)		
lack of basic laboratory services	211(57.5)	56(15.3)	100(27.2)		
Lack of facility and basic equipment	168(45.8)	69(18.8)	130(35.4)		
Lack of referral services	121(33.0)	100(27.2)	146(39.8)		
Poorly resourced facilities	266(72.5)	101(27.5)	-		
Accommodation					
Long waiting time	350(95.4)	17(4.6)	-	14.099	.000
Attitude of health care providers	301(82.0)	-	66(18.0)		
Incompetent of Staff	123(33.5)	167(45.5)	77(21.0)		
Language barrier	-	367(100.0)	-		
Acceptability					
Poor quality care	200(54.5)	134(36.5)	33(9.0)	9.832	.023
Lack of community participation	109(29.7)	67(18.3)	191(52.0)		

Table 4.2.5 shows that the chi-square value obtained for accessibility is ($x^2 = 23.965$, $p = .000$); affordability ($x^2 = 19.655$, $p = .000$); availability is ($x^2 = 31.770$, $p = .012$); accommodation is ($x^2 = 14.099$, $p = .000$); and acceptability is ($x^2 = 9.832$, $p = .023$) all at the significant levels of less than 0.05. Since these p-values were equal to or less than 0.05 values, it could be said that accessibility, affordability, availability, accommodation and acceptability are factors associated with utilization of primary health care services by reproductive age women.

Discussion

Results show that accessibility, affordability, availability, accommodation and acceptability are factors associated with utilization of primary health care services by reproductive age women. The higher a woman's level of education the more likely she is to utilize primary health care services. Study has suggested that women education at higher level is consistently associated with improved health outcome because more educated

women are better able to comprehend the importance of accessing and utilizing primary health care service (Kaba et al, 2017).

The findings of this study is supported by that of Ayamolowo, et al (2018) that accessibility is a key factor to utilisation of primary health care services related to reproductive health. Okonofua, et al (2019) who found that it was evident that reasons for non-use of PHCs for antenatal were related to perceptions about distance of PHCs, quality of PHC service delivery (costs, availability of health personnel, etc.), and partners consent to use of the facilities.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study concludes that accessibility, affordability, availability, accommodation and acceptability are factors associated with utilization of primary health care services by reproductive age women. It is therefore recommended that cost of services should be reconsidered and more funding should be provided for health in the budget. Also, availability of amenities and equipment including drugs and other consumables should be a matter of top priority.

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